

SALICYLAMIDOXIME AS AN ANALYTICAL REAGENT. PART III. SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF URANIUM

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The use of salicylamidoxime as a reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of uranium, by making use of the orange-yellow colour formed by uranium^{VI} with the reagent in alkaline solution, is described. The optimum wave-length for measurement of the colour intensity is 400 m μ ; the *pH* of the solution should be within the limit of 7.9-9.2, and an excess of the amidoxime, at least seven times the molar proportion of uranium, is essential. The colour is stable at room temperature and its intensity is independent of temperature within the range of 20°-25°, but measurements can safely be carried out at temperatures up to 30°. Beer's law holds good within the range of 7-145 p.p.m. of uranium, and sensitivity is 0.12 γ cm⁻². The composition (1:1) of the coloured species has been evaluated by Job's method and the probable constitution has been assigned. Most cations and anions interfere with the determination of uranium. Hence, a preliminary separation of uranium from the interfering ions is essential as in most other cases.

The colorimetric methods for uranium are not so sensitive as those of many other elements. Recently Yoe *et al.* (*Anal. Chem.*, 1953, 26, 1200) have proposed dibenzoylmethane, C₆H₅.CO.CH₂.CO.C₆H₅, as a colorimetric reagent for uranium, and it is the most sensitive reagent known so far. But the insolubility of the reagent in water is one great disadvantage. Of the various other substances that have been used for the colorimetric determination of uranium, mention may specially be made of salicylic acid (Müller, *Chem. Ztg.*, 1919, 43, 739), sulphosalicylic acid (Rodden, "Analytical Chemistry of the Manhattan Project," 1st. Ed., p. 121, McGraw-Hill Book Co., Inc., 1950), salicylamide (Rây *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 491), and salicylhydroxamic acid (Bhaduri, *Science & Culture*, 1952, 18, 95). The relative merits of the common colorimetric procedures for uranium have also been investigated (Rây *et al.*, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1954, Part III, p. 48).

It has already been stated in a previous communication (cf. Part I, Rây and Bandyopadhyay, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 21) that salicylamidoxime, *o*-C₆H₄(OH).C(:NOH).NH₂, develops an orange-yellow colour with uranium^{VI} in alkaline solution, which is suitable for the detection of the metal. It has therefore been considered desirable to investigate the possibility of using this substance as a reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of uranium. The optimum conditions for such a procedure have all been determined and from the results the present method appears to be quite suitable. The optimum wave-length for measurement of the colour intensity appears to be 400 m μ , where the freshly prepared solution of the reagent has no absorption. The colour intensity in presence of an excess of the amidoxime remains constant at the maximum value in the range 7.9-9.2 *pH*. Beer's law holds good over the range 7-145 p.p.m. of uranium and sensitivity (cf. Sandell, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", 2nd Ed., p. 50, Interscience Publishers, Inc., 1950) is 0.12 γ cm⁻²; while the experimental limit is 0.48 γ uranium per c.c. per cm.

The composition of the coloured product has been evaluated by Job's method (*Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113; 1936, xi, 6, 97) of 'continuous variation' as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 437; 1942, 64, 1630) and the formation of an 1:1 complex between UO_2^{2+} ion and the reagent has been indicated. Since the coloured species is insoluble in organic solvents like ether, chloroform, ethyl acetate, etc., but is highly soluble in water, it may reasonably be concluded (cf. Martell and Calvin, "Chemistry of the Metal Chelate Compounds", pp. 50-54, Prentice-Hall, Inc., 1952) that it is an ionic complex, possibly of the anionic type, as it is formed at a rather high p_H .

An attempt to determine the exact composition of the coloured species by p_H -titration method failed to furnish conclusive results, possibly owing to the fact that the complex was highly dissociated in solution, and did not provide a sharp break in the p_H -titration curve. The instability is apparent from the fact that a large excess of the reagent is necessary for the optical density of the solution to reach its maximum value, as has already been referred to.

Most common anions and cations interfere with the determination of uranium, although a few like NO_3^- , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} do not interfere at all, even when present in large amounts. The interference of cations is either due to colour-formation or precipitation of an insoluble complex or of the hydrated oxide. The approximate tolerance limits of most of the interfering ions have been determined and the results are recorded in Table III.

A previous separation of uranium from the interfering ions is necessary in this method of determination as in many other cases.

EXPERIMENTAL

A Unicam SP 600 Spectrophotometer was used for the measurement of absorption of solutions using cells of suitable thickness (5 mm., 10 mm., or 20 mm., as required) in order to have the transmittancy values within the proper range (20-80%) for minimum error. Measurements of p_H were carried out with the help of a Cambridge p_H -meter (Bench pattern) using glass electrode (for 0.9 p_H) or alkali-glass electrode (for p_H 9 and over) and a saturated calomel reference electrode.

A freshly prepared solution of pure salicylamidoxime in water (vide Part I, *loc. cit.*) was always used for the measurements. A solution of uranyl nitrate was prepared by dissolving 5 g. of $UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (A.R., B.D.H.) in 500 c.c. of water containing some nitric acid, and standardised gravimetrically by precipitation with tannic acid and igniting the precipitate to U_3O_8 . From this stock solution others of desired strengths were prepared by requisite dilution.

Stock solutions (0.1 M and 0.5 M) of caustic potash were prepared from G.R. quality KOH, and these were used for the adjustment of p_H of the solutions. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared from suitable salts (reagent-grade) and were standardised as usual. Phthalate and borate buffers (cf. Clark and Lubs, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1916, 25, 479) of p_H 3.6 and 9.2 respectively, were used to set the p_H -meter during p_H measurements.

Determination of the Optimum Wave-length for Absorption Measurements.—The absorption spectra of the coloured complex, in presence of excess of the amidoxime, at p_H 4.97 and p_H 8.72 are represented graphically in Fig. 1 along with

FIG. 1

Absorption spectra (25°).

that of the pure reagent of the same concentration at p_H 8.22. From the figure it follows that the optimum wave-length for measurement is 400 $m\mu$, where the pure reagent shows no absorption. This has therefore been used for subsequent measurements. That p_H has no influence on the absorption of the reagent is indicated by the results recorded below.

TABLE I

Salicylamidoxime = 0.005 M. Temp. = 25°.

p_H	...	4.18	5.02	6.22	7.36	8.22	9.10
Optical density per cm. (400 $m\mu$)	...	0.002	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002

Stability of the Reagent Solution.—Stock solutions (0.01M) of salicylamidoxime were prepared at different p_H values by adding acid (H_2SO_4) or alkali (KOH) as necessary and stored for several days. The optical density of each solution was measured at intervals of a day or two after adjusting the p_H of the requisite aliquot to about 8.5 and then diluting to the required volume to give a 0.005 M solution. The aqueous and alkaline solutions were found to be unstable, deteriorating readily on storing. But the acid solutions were much more stable. Thus, a 0.01M solution of the amidoxime at a p_H of 2.52 after being stored for a month and then examined as before showed an optical density of 0.022 per 2 cm.

Effect of p_H on the Colour Intensity.—Solutions containing the same concentration of uranium and the same excess of the amidoxime were prepared at different p_H values and their absorption measured at 400 m μ . The results show that the colour intensity reaches its maximum and is independent of the H⁺-ion concentration within the range 7.9 to 9.2 p_H .

Influence of Reagent Concentration on the Colour Intensity.—Solutions containing the same concentration of uranium and different quantities of the amidoxime were prepared at p_H 8.5 $\pm$ 0.1 and their optical densities measured at 400 m μ . It is observed that an excess of the reagent over seven times the molar proportion of uranium has no influence on the colour intensity.

Variation of Optical Density with the Concentration of Uranium (Beer's law).—Conformity of the system to Beer's law was investigated as usual and it was found that the system obeyed Beer's law in the range of concentration from 7.14 to 145.18 p.p.m. of uranium.

Stability of the Colour at Room Temperature.—The colour is stable at room temperature. A solution 0.0005M in UO_2^{2+} ion and 0.005M in salicylamidoxime at a p_H of 8.52 gave exactly the same optical density of 1.06 per cm., at 400 m μ , even after 72 hours of standing at room temperature.

Influence of Temperature.—The colour intensity was found to decrease appreciably over 30°, as shown below.

TABLE II

$UO_2^{2+} = 0.0005M$. Salicylamidoxime = 0.0025M. $p_H = 8.22$.

Temp.	...	20°	25°	30°	35°	40°	45°
Optical density per cm. (400 m μ)	...	0.530	0.528	0.520	0.510	0.500	0.490

Sensitivity.—Solutions containing 0.238, 0.476 and 0.714 p.p.m. of uranium showed optical densities (at 400 m μ) of 0.000, 0.008 and 0.013 per 2 cm. Hence, the corresponding values per cm. are 0.000, 0.004, and 0.007 respectively. Therefore, the smallest amount of uranium that can still be detected with the instrument is 0.48 γ . per c.c. per cm. while, the spectrophotometric sensitivity (cf. Sandell, *loc. cit.*) is 0.12 γ cm.⁻² of uranium.

Composition of the Coloured Product.—This was determined by following the method of continuous variation, first employed by Job (*loc. cit.*, cf. Vosburgh and Cooper, *loc. cit.*). In order to prevent the precipitation of uranium in solutions containing lesser amounts of salicylamidoxime (R), it was found necessary to work with very dilute solutions ($[UO_2^{2+}] + [R] = 4 \times 10^{-4}M$ in actual experiments). At this extremely low concentrations the absorption of the free UO_2^{2+} ion was found to be negligible at the wave-lengths (400 m μ & 420 m μ) used in the investigations, while the reagent did not show any absorption at these wave-lengths (cf. Fig. 1). Hence, a plot of the observed optical density against the composition of the solution, i.e. $[R]/([R] + [UO_2^{2+}])$, furnished the composition curves represented in Fig. 2. These pass through a maximum at a composition corresponding to 0.5, indicating the formation of an 1:1 complex between UO_2^{2+} ion and salicylamidoxime.

Influence of Foreign Ions on the Uranyl-salicylamidoxime Colour.—The effect of diverse ions was studied as usual and the approximate tolerance limits were determined. The latter denotes the maximum permissible concentration of the foreign ion in the solution under investigation which will affect the optical density by less than $\pm 2\%$. The results are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

$UO_2^{2+} = 0.00025M$ (59.5 p.p.m. uranium).
Salicylamidoxime = 0.0025M. $\mu_n = 8.5 \pm 0.3$. Temp. = 20°-25°.

Ion.	Added as.	Conc. of ion (p.p.m.)	Observed change in optical density.	Tolerance limit (p.p.m.).
NO_3^-	KNO_3	16,000	No change	Large excess
Cl^-	KCl	7,000	"	"
SO_4^{2-}	Na_2SO_4	24,000	"	"
$C_2O_4^{2-}$	$Na_2C_2O_4$	20	- 2%	10
CH_3COO^-	Na-acetate	4	Nil	
		30	- 2%	
		15	- 1	20
Tartrate	Na-K-tartrate	6	Nil	
		60	- 5%	
		30	- 2	20
Citrate	Na_3 -citrate	15	Nil	
		16	- 5%	
		8	- 2	6
CO_3^{2-}	Na_2CO_3	4	Nil	
		24	- 2.6%	15
		6	Nil	
BO_3^{3-}	$Na_2B_4O_7$	24	- 7.5%	
		12	- 3.6	
		6	- 1.6	6
FO_4^{3-}	Na_2HPO_4	12	- 1.6	12
		6	Nil	
		135	- 2%	
F^-	NaF	90	- 1	100
		45	Nil	
		300	+ 1.6%	200
MoO_4^{2-}	Na_2MoO_4	170	+ 4	
WO_4^{2-}	Na_2WO_4	110	+ 2	80
		11	Nil	
		10	+ 3%	
VO_3^-	NH_4VO_3	5	+ 2	3
$Cr_2O_7^{2-}$	$K_2Cr_2O_7$	2	+ 16	0
Bi^{3+}	$Bi(NO_3)_3$	2	Turbid	0
Cu^{2+}	$CuCl_2$	1	"	0
Ni^{2+}	$NiCl_2$	1	"	0
Co^{2+}	$CoCl_2$	3	+ 8%	
		1	+ 3	0
		2	+ 10	0
Mn^{2+}	$MnCl_2$	2	+ 8	0
Cr^{3+}	$CrCl_3$	2		0
Fe^{3+}	$FeCl_3$	...	Interferes at all concentrations	0
Ce^{4+}	$Ce(NO_3)_4$	1	Turbid	0
Th^{4+}	$Th(NO_3)_4$	1	"	0
Ti^{4+}	$TiO(SO_4)$	1	"	0

Procedure.—From a consideration of the experimental results recorded above, the following procedure for the estimation of uranium by salicylamidoxime may be recommended.

FIG. 2
Job's method.

UO_2^{2+} —salicylamidoxime ($p_H = 8.6 \pm 0.1$; temp. = 24°).

For the determination of uranium in commercial materials, ores, minerals, etc., a solution of the sample should be prepared and treated to separate the other elements present as usual (cf. Snell and Snell, "Colorimetric Methods of Analysis", Vol. II, pp. 490-91, D. Van Nostrand Co., Inc., 1949; Sandell, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", 2nd Ed., pp. 595-96, Interscience Publishers, Inc., 1950). The pure uranyl salt solution, as chloride, nitrate or sulphate, thus obtained, should be treated directly or in an aliquot portion with an excess (over seven times the molar proportion of uranium) of a freshly prepared solution of pure salicylamidoxime in water or dilute acid (HCl). The p_H of the solution is to be adjusted to about 8.5-9.0 by adding alkali (KOH) and then the solution diluted to a requisite volume such that the uranium content lies between 12 and 145 p.p.m.; the p_H of the final solution should be within the limit of 8.0-9.0. The optical density of the solution can then be read at 400 $m\mu$ in a cell of suitable thickness (2cm., 1cm., or 0.5 cm.) to have the optimum transmission, and the temperature should preferably be within the range of 20° to 25° . From the optical density value the concentration of uranium can be calculated from the known value of the extinction coefficient, since Beer's law is obeyed in the prescribed range of uranium concentration.

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